

ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS IN THE TERRITORY OF UZBEKISTAN AND ISSUES OF THEIR ELIMINATION.

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Abstract. In this article, the current ecological problems in our republic and the work being carried out to eliminate them were discussed on a large scale. Measures taken by the government to protect the environment of the island and the island are highlighted.

Key words: ecology, socio-ecology, Aral sea, geology, nature reserves, national parks, environmental protection.

ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ НА ТЕРРИТОРИИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА И ВОПРОСЫ ИХ УСТРАНЕНИЯ.

Аннотация. В данной статье широко обсуждаются текущие экологические проблемы в нашей республике и проводимая работа по их устранению. Освещены меры, принимаемые правительством для защиты окружающей среды острова и острова.

Ключевые слова: экология, социэкология, Аральское море, геология, заповедники, национальные парки, охрана окружающей среды.

INTRODUCTION

Protection and improvement of ecology and environment today remains one of the most urgent problems. By the end of the last century, as a result of the disturbance in the balance of relations between man and nature, the environmental and ecological situation underwent drastic changes. To protect and improve the ecology of our republic, ecological prevention of decline, restoration of the ancient ecological condition of our country, thorough study of history and the use of it in current conditions we need to look for opportunities to use it. Currently, the biosphere is changing very rapidly under the influence of human nature today. Because the forests on the earth are shrinking, at the same time trees and bushes are cut down, the land has been used for farming, it has been fertilized with drugs, and the clean air and nature have been harmed with all kinds of waste and gases. Besides floods, forest rains, dust storms and other natural processes occur in nature. All this led to the natural change and imbalance of nature.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Currently, our Republic is a large industrial and agrarian region, and further development of machine-building, energy, chemical, food industry, transport complex facing the world is planned in the future. The development of such a productive force has a negative impact on the state of social ecosystems in the Republic. The acute environmental and nature protection problems in the Republic are as follows:

- Problems of nature protection in the districts where large regional industrial complexes are located, that is, Angren-Almalik Chirchik, Fergana-Margilon, Navoi and other districts. The socio-ecological situation in these districts is not good. Because the various gases and wastes coming out in the industrial centers are causing the ecological condition of the environment to deteriorate.

- Environmental problems in the agro-industrial complex.

- Industrial discharge of natural waters with pesticides and mineral fertilizers pollution is also one of the problems.

- Problems of protection and restoration of flora and fauna, expansion of the network of nature reserves and national parks. The main strategic goals of the Republic of Uzbekistan in terms of nature protection and its rational use are: creating favorable conditions for the health of the population, maintaining the balance of production and consumption processes of renewable natural resources, production of non-renewable resources, rational use of waste; restoration of nature regeneration at regional and local levels; of nature preservation of native species and their gene pool diversity of landscapes. A catastrophic environmental problem related to the emerging Aral Sea to provide the population with quality drinking water in order to improve the economic and social situation and preserve the Aral Sea. In order to provide the inhabitants of the Aral sea with normal sanitary conditions and food, it is necessary to develop a unified water management policy together with the Central Asian countries in a short period of time, and the water that each Republic can pour into the Aral Sea, that is, all the waters of the Aral sea activities such as preservation of natural lakes are planned. The main direction of atmospheric air protection is to improve the quality of atmospheric air in cities and populated areas, then to comply with sanitary and hygienic regulations, for this, to reduce waste in all regions of our Republic, to create low-waste technologies, to create new dust collecting and cleaning devices and their development increasing output efficiency, replacing outdated devices with improvements, etc. The drying up of the Aral Sea also caused climate change. Due to the drought, the extreme continentality of the climate increased. The change in temperature between the sea and the land, the increase in the wind speed, led to the strengthening of the water wave phenomenon.

- Mammals and birds have declined. Arid fields are becoming infested with rodents that spread dangerous diseases. The sanitary-epidemiological situation of the island is becoming extremely serious. If the problems arising in nature are not solved immediately, the life of humanity and the whole creature will be in danger. We are dependent on nature, we cannot live without nature, so we should all protect nature, protect every inch of it like the apple of an eye, use natural resources wisely, use every drop of water sparingly, always take care of nature. we have to do it.

- In the President's speech on July 12, 2017, at the meeting with the Oliy Majlis Chambers, political parties and representatives of the environmental movement of Uzbekistan, the representative authorities, political parties and the Ecological Movement were discussed. the activities of the period were analyzed in a critical spirit, and the important tasks ahead of us regarding the deepening of the reforms were defined. In particular, the future tasks of the Ecological Movement and its deputy group in the Legislative Chamber were clearly indicated.

CONCLUSION

- First of all, creation of new laws related to the field, improvement of the existing ones, strengthening of control and analysis activities at the level of today's demand. development of the concept of continuous environmental education, development of the system of public inspectors of environmental control, implementation of systematic work aimed at improving the environmental culture of the population, and the program of measures for conducting an inventory of objects and water treatment facilities that have a harmful effect on the environment accepted and consistently applied to life. Also, in connection with the implementation of the part of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Water and Water Use" on the use of water bodies for consumption, household and other needs of the population, the Ministries of Health and Housing and Communal Services , Ecology and environmentThe program of 10 measures has been adopted and is being consistently implemented. Also, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Water and Water Use" regarding the implementation of the part of the use of water bodies for consumption, household and other needs of the population. Ministries of Health and Housing and Communal Services, Ecology and Environment.

- Parliamentary hearings were held on the information of the State Committees for Protection, Geology and Mineral Resources. At the same time, the status of implementation of the Basel Convention on "Transboundary Transportation of Hazardous Wastes and Control over their Disposal" was studied, and a hearing of the Committee on Ecology and Environmental Protection was organized.

- It is clear that the tasks ahead of us are extremely difficult. Their successful implementation requires each of us to use all our knowledge and skills, to be more precise, to live on the path of the development of our country.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh. M. Action strategy on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021. 2. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev "Ecology and environment.
2. Decree on improving the state management system in the field of environmental protection. April 21, 2017, Tashkent
3. Kayumov A.A., Rakhmonov R.N., Egamberdieva L.SH., Khamrokulov J.H. Use and protection of nature. - T.: "Economics", 2014.
4. Nigmatov A.N. theoretical foundations of ecology. Study guide for the field of study and specialty of ecology and environmental protection.-responsible editor b.f.d. A.S. Yuldashev - T., 2013.
5. Ergasheva, Y. A., Vasieva. D. I., & Murtazova, S. B. (2019). Political persecutions and ideological pressure on the creative intellectuals of Uzbekistan in post-war decades. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, 8(2 \$10), 374-377.